

Ionic Reactions in Thionyl Chloride. Part II. Mechanism of Reactions of Solvo-bases and Solvo-acids

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Mechanism of reactions of solvo-acids and solvo-bases in thionyl chloride as a solvent has been discussed to explain the formation of complexes, particularly by stannic chloride and pyridine with base/acid mole ratios of 1:1, 2:1, 3:1, and 4:1. The polar character of thionyl chloride, indicating its autoionisation, is useful in explaining the neutralisation reactions involving not more than two moles of the base for each mole of the acid. Existence of an equilibrium, just after this simple neutralisation reaction comprising at least three species, the relative amounts of which will depend on a number of factors, is presumed in solution and may be depicted as:

The desolvation of solid complexes and the reaction of the complex in solution with more moles of the base may be expressed on the basis of forms (II) and (III). The reaction of form (III) with more base entails ionisation of chloride ion to account for changes in conductance of the solution and this reaction goes to displacement of two chloride ions by two base molecules. This view does not violate the hexacovalency of tin otherwise the ion SnCl_6^{4-} is to be presumed, which does not find favour with the known facts.

In a previous communication¹ the polar nature of thionyl chloride, which emerges from a consideration of its physical properties and radic-chlorine exchange studies, has been useful in explaining the behaviour of solvo-acids and ansolvo-bases in this solvent. Incidentally, the reactions involved in that discussion constituted very simple systems of acid-base neutralisation reactions. Literature, however, records some reactions of the Lewis acids and bases in thionyl chloride, which require more elaborate studies in order to explain their intriguing behaviour.

Pease and Luder², who studied the neutralisation of stannic chloride and pyridine conductometrically in thionyl chloride, postulated the following mode of ionisation to explain the changes in conductance of the solution.

Spandau and Brunneck³ studied this reaction conductometrically as well as potentiometrically and proposed the following mechanism for the neutralisation reaction, which takes in account the polar character of the solvent:

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1. Sandhu *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1960, **37**, 329.

2. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 5195.

3. *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1955, **278**, 197.

These workers also reported that conductometric titration between pyridine or quinoline and stannic chloride in thionyl chloride indicated breaks with base/acid mole ratios of 1:1, 2:1, 3:1, and 4:1 (pyridine only).

A digression to examine some relevant facts might be useful for discussing the results and views of the aforementioned workers in the light of observations recorded in the present investigation. At present, there is no direct evidence as to the nature of bonding in the solvates⁴ $\text{UCl}_4 \cdot \text{SOCl}_2$ and $\text{ZrCl}_4 \cdot \text{SOCl}_2$. Recently, some data on the solvate of titanium tetrachloride with acetyl chloride have been made available. The carbonyl stretching frequency in the solvate, $\text{TiCl}_4 \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{COCl}$, indicates a considerable lowering as compared to that of the pure acetyl chloride. The decrease in the value of force constant for carbonyl bond from 11.75m dyn/Å in acetyl chloride to 9.05m dyn/Å in $\text{TiCl}_4 \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{COCl}$, evidently leads to a lowering of bond order by about 21% in the solvate⁵. In case the solvate exists as an ion pair (II), the reverse should be expected⁶.

(I)

(II)

The dipole moment, 1.60D at 20°, and dielectric constant, 9.25 at 20°, of thionyl chloride⁷ are lower than those of acetyl chloride, 2.40D⁸ and 15.9⁹ at 20° respectively. The absence of solid solvates of thionyl chloride with pyridine etc. and existence of the corresponding solvates with acetyl chloride¹⁰ justify the more polar character of acetyl chloride. Selenium oxychloride, having more electrical conductance¹¹, (2×10^{-6}) and higher dielectric constant¹² (46 at 20°) than those of thionyl chloride¹³, 3.5×10^{-9} and 9.25 respectively, form solid solvates with pyridine etc.¹⁴ The force constant of sulphur-

4. Hecht *et al.*, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1947, **254**, 255; Bradley *et al.*, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1957, **3**, 367.
5. Cassimatis and Susz, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1961, **44**, 943.
6. Cassimatis and Susz, *ibid.*, 1960, **43**, 424; Cook, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1950, **37**, 48.
7. Beyaert and Govert, *Chem. Abs.*, 1938, **32**, 6517.
8. Koehl and Wenzke, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **59**, 1418.
9. International Critical Tables, 1926, VI, 82.
10. Sandhu *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 315.
11. Julien, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, **47**, 1799.
12. Wildish, *ibid.*, 1920, **42**, 2607.
13. Spandau *et al.*, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1952, **270**, 201.
14. Jackson and Smith, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **62**, 544.

chlorine bond, 2.80 m dyn/Å, in thionyl chloride is larger than that of selenium-chlorine bond, 2.59 m dyn/Å, indicating higher bond order between the former, which points to its less polar character in comparison to that of selenium oxychloride¹⁵. These facts lead to the conclusion that thionyl chloride appears to possess less polar character than those of acetyl chloride and selenium oxychloride. In view of the foregoing discussion, it may be tentatively assumed that, in the solvates of thionyl chloride, the bonding is most probably between the metal and oxygen just as in the solvate of acetyl chloride and titanium tetrachloride.

The present investigation has been taken up for two considerations. Firstly, to see which of the four complexes in solution reported for pyridine and stannic chloride in thionyl chloride is most stable. Secondly, the role of the solvent in acid/base neutralisation reaction can be partly understood by actual isolation and characterisation of the stable complex. In order to elucidate the mechanism of reaction, the stability of the complex in solution is deemed to provide some interesting information. The four breaks in conductometric titration were recorded when the base solution was added to the acid solution. In these four complexes, the stability factors, which influence the formation of a particular complex, can be partly disentangled by adding acid solution to the base solution during conductance measurements. The most stable complex would be formed first because there are adequate chances for an acid molecule to take up as many molecules of the base as it could afford to bind. The curves in Fig. 1 illustrate the formation of the most stable complexes of pyridine, quinoline, and isoquinoline with stannic chloride in thionyl chloride with an acid/base mole ratio of 1:2. Nevertheless, with pyridine and isoquinoline, the indication about the existence of the acid complex is more conspicuous as compared to quinoline. This may be correlated with their base strengths as is discussed later on.

FIG. 1

¹⁵ Späthert, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1954, 275, 210.

To investigate the role of the solvent during an acid/base neutralisation reaction, especially when solvo-acids and solvo-bases are involved, isolation of the stable complex, as indicated by conductometric titration and its analysis, is expected to show the presence or absence of the solvent molecule (or molecules) in the solid complex which may help in ascertaining the nature of the mechanism. The stability of the complex, as envisaged in solution and actually found in solid phase, might indicate the function of the solvent during and after the neutralisation process. The solvo-bases, pyridine, quinoline, and isoquinoline, have been employed in preparing the complexes of solvo-acids, titanium tetrachloride, zirconium tetrachloride, and stannic chloride, in thionyl chloride. These complexes were isolated and characterised by analysis. The results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Complex:	M.P.	Colour.	% Metal.		% Chlorine.		% Nitrogen.	
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
$(C_5H_5N)_2TiCl_4 \cdot SOCl_2$	226-202°	Grey	10.33	10.28	45.61	45.64	5.45	6.96
* $(C_9H_7N)_2TiCl_4$	177-79°	Dirty pink	9.87	10.71	31.91	31.69	5.64	6.25
† $(C_9H_7N)_2TiCl_4 \cdot SOCl_2$	176-78°	Red	9.31	9.46	34.62	35.01	4.89	5.52
$(C_5H_5N)_2ZrCl_4 \cdot SOCl_2$	320° (d)	Dirty white	17.70	17.84	41.90	41.76	4.94	5.49
* $(C_9H_7N)_2ZrCl_4$	280 (d)	Do	18.55	18.53	29.00	28.92	5.23	5.70
† $(C_9H_7N)_2ZrCl_4 \cdot SOCl_2$	160-62°	Do	14.80	14.92	34.69	34.92	4.21	4.50
$(C_5H_5N)_2SnCl_4 \cdot SOCl_2$	280-82°	Yellow	22.10	22.06	39.05	39.60	4.79	5.20
* $(C_9H_7N)_2SnCl_4$	230° (d)	Grey	22.92	22.87	27.40	27.36	4.84	5.39
† $(C_9H_7N)_2SnCl_4$	235° (d)	White	22.57	22.87	27.54	27.36	4.66	5.39

Some of these complexes decompose without melting and others melt with decomposition.

*Quinoline complex.

†Isoquinoline complex.

Table I shows the striking behaviour of pyridine, which forms complexes with all the three solvo-acids with the retention of one molecule of the solvent in the solid phase under ordinary conditions. On the other hand, quinoline is unique in forming complexes with all the three solvo-acids without any molecule of the solvent. The behaviour of isoquinoline is almost intermediate, evidently due to the relative strengths of these bases in this solvent. This is almost in order of their base strengths in aqueous solutions in which the pK_a values are: pyridine, 5.14; quinoline, 4.85; isoquinoline, 5.14¹⁶. Thus, the conductometric titrations as well as isolation of complexes present ample evidence in support of the mechanism involving ionisation of the solvent, solvo-acids, and solvo-bases so far as the complexes with acid/base mole ratio of 1:2 (or 1:1) are concerned. The desolvation of complexes (complete or incomplete), which are quite stable in solution, points, however, to the slightly polar nature of thionyl chloride. Any rigorous comparison between highly polar solvents, such as water, and slightly polar solvents, such as thionyl chloride, seems to be unwarranted. In case of the latter, it is safe to surmise that these can play the dual role of polar as well as simple solvents.

The complexes of pyridine and quinoline with stannic chloride in thionyl chloride with base mole ratios more than 2 cannot be reconciled with the aforementioned mecha-

nism. The most serious objection is to the existence of ion SnCl_5^{4-} , which is to be presumed. This assumption on the basis of Pauling's electroneutrality principle¹⁷ is not feasible. Energetically, the accumulation of four units of negative charge precludes disintegration of SnCl_5^{4-} under the influence of repulsive forces between negatively charged ligands. Of course, the existence of SnCl_5^{3-} ions has been undoubtedly proved¹⁸. However, there are certain complex ions^{19,20} such as $\text{Mo}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}$ and $\text{Zr}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_4^{4-}$, which have apparently a high negative charge. The former involves a π -bonding ligand and here the metal feeds back its negative charge through $d\pi-p\pi$ interaction. In case of the latter, the metal atom has got vacant inner d orbitals which might be suitable for bond formation and also the stability may be enhanced due to chelation or entropy effect. The complex (diarsine)₂- TiCl_4 is one of the other examples of eight co-ordination in which a π -bonding ligand stabilises higher co-ordination²¹.

Spandau and Brunneck³ explained the formation of complexes with base mole ratios more than 2 on the assumption that complex species such as $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{N})_2\text{SO}^{2+}$ and $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{N})_2\text{SO}^{2+}$ were taking part in the neutralisation reaction. This assumption does not seem to be compatible with the facts. Firstly, on the basis of this assumption, the nature of base should not affect the number of base moles per acid mole, which is contrary to the experimental evidence. Secondly, the ionisation of thionyl chloride to SO^{2+} is not preferred as after the ionisation of the first chloride ion, the second chlorine is more firmly bound and cannot ionise under ordinary conditions. This type of reaction can take place under drastic and irreversible conditions (for instance, $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_3 + \text{SOCl}_2 \longrightarrow 2\text{NaCl} + 2\text{SO}_2$).

This situation leads one to make certain reasonable assumptions which should be based on some indirect evidence. Thus, it is plausible to assume the existence of an equilibrium between various complex species in solution as soon as the simple neutralisation reaction is complete, which is the first phase when the solvent is effectively acting as an ionising medium. The existence of these species, the relative amounts of which are dependent on equilibrium conditions such as concentration, temperature etc., may be visualised as under:

The solid complex retains or loses the solvent molecules to achieve more stability which is dictated by entropy, lattice forces, etc. All the three species, presumed in equilibrium with one another, have been detected in solution or in solid phase in different acid-base systems (Table I). In case the loss of solvent by a solid complex is considered to take place stepwise, the importance of forms (II) and (III) is realised. Intrinsically this approach is logical and consequently the co-ordination number does not suffer any change. The occurrence of breaks corresponding to three and four moles of the base during conductometric titration may be explained on the assumption that form (III) is actively engaged

17. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 1461.

18. Dickinson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 276.

19. Pauling, "Nature of the Chemical Bond", Cornell Univ. Press, New York, 1960, 3rd ed., p. 177.

20. Hoard et al., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 4203.

21. Clark et al., *Nature*, 1961, 192, 222.

in the reaction with additional amounts of the base and the extent of the reaction is characteristic of the base. Thus pyridine, which is a stronger base than quinoline, forms complexes containing up to four mole ratios of the base, whereas quinoline goes up to three mole ratios only. The reaction mechanism may be exemplified for pyridine as:

In these reactions of the complex with more base, the function of thionyl chloride is only that of a simple solvent which does not influence the interacting species except that to provide a medium. This reaction of base with complex species is governed by an interaction between dipole-dipole and ion-dipole forces. The displacement of chloride ion by base molecules cannot be continued beyond a certain limit because, with the removal of first chloride ion, the remaining metal-chlorine bonds become stronger than that before due to back-donation by chlorine. Thus the resulting π -bonding raises the bond order between chlorine and metal. It is apparent from the conductometric titrations¹ that at the most two chloride ions can be displaced by two base molecules, which is dependent on the strength of the base.

EXPERIMENTAL

Thionyl chloride was purified as described in Part I¹ and due precautions were taken in handling the solvent for conductivity work as well as in the preparation of complexes.

Zirconium tetrachloride, supplied by Johnson Matthey and Co., Ltd., London, was used as such and stannic chloride and titanium tetrachloride were purified as already mentioned¹.

Pyridine, quinoline, and isoquinoline were kept over solid potassium hydroxide overnight and distilled in a current of dry nitrogen. Freshly distilled samples were used.

In the preparation of the complexes, the procedure described earlier¹ was followed. Titanium, zirconium, and tin were estimated as dioxides. Chlorine was determined by Volhard's method. The analysis of nitrogen was carried by the method of Jackson and Smith¹⁴. The melting points are uncorrected. The conductivity apparatus was the same as used previously¹.

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